

ON POWERS FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF ALTERNATION

Hermann Burmann

Abstracts

A perspective on power is presented with an emphasis on its rotation. The effects of rotation could be fully deduced by mathematics students at the high school level. This rotation in calculation procedures and its consequences do not deviate at all from the traditional concept of power, but lead to a more abstract one.

Keywords: power; mathematics; perspective; rotation.

1 Introduction

Are there any properties of exponents that we don't use because we are unaware of their existence? In mathematics literature, there are trivial concepts that are known by students and used in the context of exponents. But there are concepts that they don't use due to their mathematical implications.

Examples of this are exponential functions in the form e^x , and complex exponentiation, present in Euler's Formula ($e^{ix} = \cos(x) + i \sin(x)$). Another example is mathematical indeterminacies of the type 0^0 . So everything seems to point to the fact that, given the more challenging implications for common sense, certain notions are avoided in the context of powers. Hence we question: are there still more properties of powers that are hidden?

According to Iezzi et al. [1], exponentiation is fundamental to mathematics, as it establishes the simplified notation for a homogeneous product, with the exponent indicating

repetitions of the base in multiplication. Dante [2], defines power in a similar way: "exponentiation is the operation by which we associate two numbers a (base) and n (exponent), a third number a^n (power), which is the product of n factors equal to a , when $n \geq 2$ ".

Similarly, Bianchini [3], presents power as a product of identical factors, clarifying that the exponent indicates how many times the base is used in the multiplication. Furthermore, according to Boyer [4], the history of mathematics documents that the concept of power was only standardized from the mid-17th century onwards, with mathematicians such as René Descartes.

However, other mathematicians continue to work to refine the concept of power. An example of this is that Guidorizzi [5] approaches exponentiation as an exponential function in the context of mathematical analysis, extending the concept of power to the set of real numbers.

A power is, in short, a multiplication of a number (let's call it base b) by itself depending on its potential elevation (let's call it exponent e). Considering the possibility of more hidden properties, have we been dealing with a reductionist view of power all this time?

This work explores a new perspective on power that can be experienced by high school students and extended to other mathematical concepts.

2 Theoretical Foundation

We base our theory of power on the Axiom of Cancellation. Through this axiom, we derive some similar logical consequences, such as the following:

1. If self-multiplication can be canceled without algebraic operations, the power in question is in direct alternating form, that is, the base and the exponent invert their positions, so that one becomes the other;

2. If the power is alternating in a direct manner, there is nothing that cancels it, except explicit algebraic operations or a new alternation;

3. There is no self-multiplication that is independent of the absence of alternation or algebraic operations that cancel it out;

4. If there is nothing that cancels a self-multiplication, then the power is alternating and without algebraic operations that derive it;

5. A power only exists in relation to another power that was canceled out by the alternation that gave rise to it.

The big question is how can we show the alternation between powers, given that the base and the exponent always remain in the same place.

From these axioms we will conceive the theory of so-called "rotating powers". Through the previous axioms themselves, we have a definition for them: rotating powers are powers that, when rotated, alternate from one power to another, by canceling one of them, without resorting to algebraic operations as a form of differentiation.

This idea was inspired by a dream I had a few years ago. In that dream, there was a power x^n that, in addition to rotating, moved in opposite directions all the time, so that it was transformed into another power u^x (this is the visual effect of x^n when turned upside down). With the rotation again, there was a return to the original power and a reciprocal conversion.

After a series of experiments with numbers and other reflections, I understood that a power could alternate into another power, under certain imposed conditions. And I called these powers rotatable.

The behavior of a rotating power can be observed exactly as in my dream. To do this, we simply need to consider the original power x^n in a circle, which will be rotated in an arc of 180° , as shown in the illustration below:

Fig 1. Rotated power

Some interesting effects occur in rotational powers, and we will discuss this further later. Regarding rotation, we also created the concept of "exponential rotation," which is mentioned in calculation procedures.

Students with prior knowledge of powers may find more information about the rotating form of powers. If initially one has $b \neq e$ (different base from the exponent), exponential rotation results in a new power, which is formed exclusively by metathesis (exchange of places) caused by the rotation. Thus, with exponential rotation, we will have the consequence that:

Fig.2Consequence of exponential rotation.

In other words, the old base becomes a new exponent, and the old exponent, a new base. And the metathesis resulting from exponential rotation does not affect or interfere with the concept of power. It is this rotation of the exponent until it assumes the role of a new base that defines exponential rotation. In calculation procedures, it is represented by a rotation symbol around a power or by the expression "Exp rot" before it.

When we test with numbers, we have an observation that needs to be intelligibly organized and considered as a legitimate power. Let's look at an example:

Fig 3.Visual effect of rotational power.

Notice that rotating 2^3 causes the images of these numbers to be upside down, but we know that the values remain the same, just in a different position. What appears to be the Greek letter epsilon is actually a 3, while what appears to be the letter tau is a 2. In this sense, the resulting power is that of 3^2 .

3 Aspects of Exponential Rotation

With exponential rotation, self-multiplication usually cancels out in the original power, and permissibility changes in the subsequent power. For this to happen, the value of the base must be different from that of the exponent. Let's illustrate:

$$\text{Exp rot } 5^2 \rightarrow 2^5$$

Here, with the exponential rotation at the original power, the product $5 \cdot 5$ is cancelled and replaced by $2 \cdot 2 \cdot 2 \cdot 2 \cdot 2$. For the first power to be activated, it is necessary to alternate with it again, via exponential rotation. From this we arrive at the following conclusion: it is implicit that the permissibility of self-multiplication of a number is mediated by alternation, so that there is a power.

Up to this point, we have described the condition for the existence of a power. Another surprising fact is that, through exponential rotation, we can convert one power into another without the need for elementary operations (which are fundamental to the properties of powers). Examples of properties (which are also laws) of powers are these:

$$\text{Power of power: } (a^m)^n = a^{mn}$$

$$\text{Power, by dividing powers with the same base: } a^m / a^n = a^{m-n}$$

$$\text{Power, as a product of powers with the same base: } a^m \cdot a^n = a^{m+n}$$

Among these properties, we should also include rotational power, which allows converting one power into another without elementary operations. We suggest one more property: Alternating power. For most situations in which $b \neq e$ we will have to:

$$\text{Exp rot } a^m \rightarrow m^a; \text{ Exp rot } a^m \neq a^m$$

This perspective of alternating from one power to another should be introduced in other topics, such as certain problems involving exponential equations. However, it is necessary to emphasize that for exponential rotation to guarantee the transformation of one power into another, the condition $b \neq e$ is not sufficient. It is also necessary that:

$$b \neq 4 \text{ and } e \neq 2, \text{ or that } b \neq 2 \text{ and } e \neq 4$$

That's because : $\text{Exp rot } 2^4 = \text{Exp rot } 4^2$. This is a case where, despite the base and exponent values being different, exponential rotation does not convert one power into another. It is likely that exponential rotation may somehow add another level of difficulty to problems involving powers and exponential equations. Regarding the problem "convert 4^2 to a power of base 2", traditional teaching provides the following answer: $16 = 2^2 \cdot 2^2$. Then :

$$4^2 = (2^2)^2 = 2^4$$

Algebraic operations are unavoidable. But, by exponential rotation, we have that: $4^2 = \text{Exp rot } 4^2 \rightarrow 2^4$. Here we performed the conversion, by alternating, of 4^2 into a power of base 2, without using any algebraic operation.

By the way, if we ask artificial intelligence whether it is possible to convert one power into another without the condition of elementary operations, it may answer us: "if you don't want to use any elementary operations (multiplication, division, root extraction, logarithm, algebraic substitution or basic algebraic manipulation), then it is not possible because converting one power into another normally requires these operations."

Since the artificial intelligence itself was not trained to address the logic of rotatable powers, its response had to be based on the traditional teaching of powers.

However, powers should have long been taught alongside rotatable powers, as this would give students a broader and more abstract perspective on the concept of power, one that is not limited to elementary operations.

4 Conclusion

Rotational powers are mathematical perspectives that cannot be ignored by teachers or hidden at the secondary level, as if they were something that could harm the traditional teaching of powers. On the contrary, we have seen that the properties of powers are complemented by rotational powers.

In fact, there would be no confusion among students with the introduction of this power model if the definition of exponential rotation were given to them. With exponential rotation, despite the numbers being upside down, there is a cognitive effort involved in organizing them in a potential way, that is, interpreting the effects that will define another power to be analyzed.

Therefore, rotating powers should continue to stimulate mathematical reasoning from a different perspective, beyond the molds of traditional teaching, promoting metacognition among students.

References

[1]IEZZI, Gelson et al. Mathematics. Single Volume. 3rd ed. São Paulo: Saraiva, 2004.

[2]DANTE, L.R. Mathematics: Context & Applications. Single Volume. São Paulo: Editora Ática, 2005.

[3]BIANCHINI, Eduardo. Mathematics. Single Volume. 2nd ed. São Paulo: Moderna, 2004.

[4]BOYER, Carl Benjamin. History of Mathematics. 2nd ed. São Paulo: Edgard Blücher, 1996.

[5]GUIDORIZZI, Hamilton Luiz. A Course in Calculus. Volume 1. 5th ed. Rio de Janeiro: LTC, 2001.